

HISTORY OF ORIGIN AND SOCIAL AND PEDAGOGICAL NEED OF TUTOR'S ACTIVITY

Nurmatova Madina

Teacher of the Kokand State Pedagogical Institute.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8357975>

Annotation: This article presents the history of tutoring and its role in the education system of the countries of the world.

Key words: tutor, history of tutoring, tutoring phenomenon.

In the currently developing global education system, the role of tutoring in creating the effectiveness of the learning and upbringing process is incomparable. Since we are studying the history of tutoring, the etymology of its origin, it is appropriate to turn to the history of tutoring. It can be seen that tutor activity originated in ancient Greece and was widely used as a form of informal pedagogical support. The main goal of the tutor was to transform knowledge in order to help the student acquire skills in the chosen field. Lessons were often improvised.

In the 14th century, tutorship was formed in the classical British universities - Oxford and a little later Cambridge. Since then, tutoring has been considered an established form of mentoring. At Oxford and Cambridge, tutors continue to play an important role in the teaching and learning process.

Tutor (English: guide) means "home teacher, tutor, (school) teacher".

Tutoring as one of the institutional forms of education appeared in the first British universities: Oxford (XII century) and Cambridge (XIII century).

Until 1917, tutoring was used only in home schooling, in connection with the German model of university education in Russia.

Tutor - (lat. tutorem - teacher, educator) in the meaning of "appointed by the elders to take care of the younger ones" has been recorded in sources since 1580.

The phenomenon of tutoring is closely connected with the history of European universities and is characterized by the fact that it originated in the UK. It should be recognized that its task is to combine the content of student life with academic ideals in practice. It was not until the 17th century that the scope of tutoring began to expand. Educational functions became more and more important in it.

The tutor gave advice on which lectures and practical classes are more effective for the student, how to draw up a curriculum, and also monitored student progress and preparation for university exams.

Since the 17th century, the tutoring system has been officially recognized as part of the English university system, and in the 18th and 20th centuries was central to the formation of England's oldest universities.

The lecture system served only as an addition to it. Thus, a tutor is a historically established pedagogical position that provides the opportunity to develop individual

educational programs for pupils and students that accompany the process of individual development in schools, universities, systems of additional and continuing education.

In Russia, tutoring appeared much later than in Western culture. The local education system initially did not envisage a separate figure of the tutor. A similar format happened, for example, in monasteries. Elders were attached to the monks, they taught the students, communicated with them one by one. Educators from aristocratic families of pre-revolutionary Russia joined the tradition of monastic mentors. They literally directed education, taught and helped to find their way in life. Tutors, like patrons, have spent a lot of money to develop tutoring in Russia.

The English word "tutor" was coined by the Anglophile M.N. Thanks to Katkov, she officially entered teaching practice. In the 19th century, the institution of group tutors was introduced, its tasks included organizing activities, monitoring the development of guardians and educating pupils of moral and spiritual qualities. But the history of tutoring in Russia did not end there, it was reformed in the 1980s, it reappeared as an independent pedagogical movement.

Tutorism today is an innovative element in the post-Soviet space, which has not yet been implemented everywhere. The main trends in the development of tutoring in Russia show that it is organized as part of individual training, often at a distance

In addition, there are tutoring centers in large educational institutions - for example, in higher education institutions, the use of tutors seems to be more efficient as demand increases.

At Foxford Home Online School, where young people from all over the world study remotely, the tutor is a teacher with a unique role. We continue the tradition of individual work with students.

Tutors are designed to help students determine the trajectory of development, find themselves and love learning. All Foxford Online Homeschool teachers have degrees in psychology and education and have many years of experience.

Tutoring at Foxford starts with a specially designed diagnostic Skillfolio. This helps the educator to find out the interests of young people and choose an individual educational trajectory. The test shows what professional roles the child is suitable for and what skills he needs to develop in order to succeed.

Studying the activity of tutoring, established in Russia, one can see that it developed in the following chronological order:

1989-1990 - project of the tutor faculty of the School of Cultural Policy (P.G. Shchedrovitsky), Moscow.

1991 - the first group of tutors was created at the school "Eureka-development" (supervisor Kovaleva T.M.), Tomsk.

1996-2013, 2016 - All-Russian scientific and practical tutor conferences (Tomsk).

2007 - the Interregional Tutor Association was created.

2008 - entry of the profession "tutor" into the register of professions, the nomenclature of positions.

Since 2008 - international tutor conferences in Moscow.

2010 - opening of the master's program for the preparation of tutors (MPGU).

2011-2017 - development of a corporate standard for vocational training.

2012 - The concept of a tutor model of learning became one of the winners of the Skolkovo schools competition.

2012-2015 - project "Development of a system for assessing the quality of conditions for the individualization of education", FIP MES RF.

2012 - FIRST summer tutoring university in Gelendzhik.

2013 - training program for specialists in the field of individualization and tutoring according to MTA corporate standards.

2015 - Opening of the Department of Individualization and Tutoring (MGGU).

2015 - ANO DPO together with "PrESTO" held the first All-Russian competition "Coach of the Year".

2016 - A cooperation agreement was signed with the International Association of Financial and Economic Education Organizations - "Tutor for Financial Literacy".

2017 - the professional standard "Specialist in the field of education" was approved, which includes the generalized labor function "Tutor support for students".

2017 - MTA won the Presidential grant for the implementation of the project "Professional and public examination of the quality of individualization of education and tutoring."

2018 - The first master's program in tutoring in Russia was transferred from Moscow State Pedagogical University to Moscow State Pedagogical University

2019 - MTA won a Presidential grant for the implementation of the project "Tutor Hackathon: a platform for the development and testing of technologies for individualization and personalization of learning."

2019 - ANO DPO together with "PrESTO" holds the third All-Russian competition "Tutor of the Year".

2019 - LUT in Tomsk.

2020 - MTA won a Presidential Grant for the implementation of the Self-Education Skills project - an intensive tutor training course.

2020 - LUT in Gelendzhik.

2021 - The Board of the ITA and the Directorate of ANO DPO "PrESTO" adopted the Tutor Code of Conduct.

2022 - LUT "Ecosystem of tutoring in the Russian Federation: specialization, division of labor and networking". Format: online, offline, hybrid, face-to-face.

In the Republic of Uzbekistan, since September 2021, tutoring activities have begun in a number of higher educational institutions. In particular, the Tashkent State University of Law, the National University of Uzbekistan, the Uzbek State University of World Languages, the Tashkent State University named after Nizomi were among the first to create tutoring staffs and began tutoring activities. Also in Uzbekistan, the priority is to improve the policy of working with youth, "educating an intellectually developed young generation as a comprehensively developed personality", harmonizing the quality of education and criteria for its assessment in higher educational institutions with international standards. "In-depth study of sciences" tasks were defined.

When implementing these tasks, tutors are regularly engaged in the spiritual, moral and professional education of students; constantly improve their qualifications, professional training, theoretical knowledge and work experience; respect for the honor, dignity and labor

reputation of students; professors and teachers in an educational institution try not to allow student prestige and authority to be tarnished.

In the last years in our republic, "obeschit vysokiy uroven i kachestvo training kadrov, v sovershenstve vladeyushchikh sovremennymi information-communication technologies and foreign languages; the organization of scientific and research work and higher educational institutions, the increase of efficiency, the wide implementation of the results of research and practice, the provision of mutual integration of education, science and production, the attraction of talented young people to scientific and research work, and greater attention is paid to bilateral support. At the same time, it is important to raise the educational process to an innovative level and to form in students the skills necessary for future activities, based on the use of advanced forms of education.

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